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HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE STUDY OF MAHMUD AL-KASHGHARI'S LEGACY: RESEARCH IN TURKISH, EUROPEAN, AND RUSSO-SOVIET ORIENTAL STUDIES

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Abstract

*This article examines the historiography of scholarship on the legacy of the great 11th-century Turkic scholar Mahmud al-Kashghari and his monumental work *Diwan Lughat al-Turk*. The study identifies three key dimensions of Kashghari studies: the ethno-cultural history of Turkic peoples between the 9th and 12th centuries; the history of the Kara-Khanid Khanate; and the scholarly analysis of the *Diwan* itself as a primary source. The article traces, in chronological order, the academic contributions of Turkish, German, Russian-Soviet, and Uzbek scholars, including translations, publications, and research papers. Particular emphasis is placed on the significance of the 1915 Istanbul lithographic edition for global Oriental studies, and on the early scholarly responses from Turkey, Europe, and Russia.*

Keywords: *Mahmud al-Kashghari, Diwan Lughat al-Turk, Kashghari studies, Kara-Khanid Khanate, history of Turkic peoples, Oriental studies, historiography, 9th–12th centuries, Turkology, source studies.*

INTRODUCTION

The complex nature of the question concerning the study of Mahmud al-Kashghari's era and legacy is evident. First, this issue is related to reflecting the ethno-cultural history of the Turkic peoples in the period between the 9th and 12th centuries. Second, works that study Mahmud al-Kashghari himself — the Kara-Khanid Khanate in which he lived, the great state of the Seljuk sultans to which he later moved, the Abbasid Caliphate in Baghdad whose capital he witnessed, and their history during the mid and late 11th century — must be mentioned. Third, the history of studying the work of Mahmud al-Kashghari itself — which began entering broad scholarly circulation from 1915 — and the history of its translation into other languages must be examined anew. On the first two points, entire scholarly institutions have worked and various research projects have been conducted in different countries, with dissertations

defended. It is impossible to even briefly mention all of them. We may add only that for a broader acquaintance with earlier research on the political history of the Kara-Khanid Khanate, one may consult the work of Professor Omurqul Qaroev (15.10.1930 – 18.09.2002), who defended in Tashkent the first doctoral dissertation in Central Asia on the political history of that state.

The most important works in the field of the history of Turkic peoples belong to Academician V.V. Bartold (1869–1930), and his contemporaries V.V. Radlov (1837–1918), Iosif Marquart (1864–1930), N. Aristov (1847 – after 1918), Ahmad Zaki Validi Togan (1890–1970), Karl Brockelmann (1868–1956), S.Ye. Malov (1880–1957), V.A. Gordlevsky (1876–1956), V.F. Minorsky (1877–1966), and in the second half of our century — the Ukrainian Orientalist Omeljan Pritsak (07.04.1919 – 29.05.2006), the Azerbaijani Orientalist Ziya M. Buniyatov (24.12.1921 – 21.02.1997), the Turkish scholars Faruk Sumer (05.11.1924 – 21.10.1995) and Reshat Gench, the Russian archaeologist Yuliy S. Khudyakov (born 1946), the Russian Orientalist Sergey Grigoryevich Agajanov (1928–1998), the Kazakhstani scholars Bulat Eshmukhambetovich Kumekov, Satay Sidiqov, S.M. Akhinjanov (1939–1991), the Kazakhstani archaeologist Karl Moldakhmetovich Baipakov, and the Uzbek historians Academician Buribay Ahmadov (1924–2002), Karim Shaniyazov (1924 – 05.10.2000), and others.

In Uzbekistan, various research projects have been conducted on the political history, economy, culture, numismatics, and archaeological monuments of the Kara-Khanid period, as well as on the origins of the Uzbek ethnos and the settlement of Uzbek groups in Eastern Tian Shan during the Kara-Khanid era. Research has also been conducted in China and its Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region on the history of Turkic ethnoses in Eastern Tian Shan and Inner Asia. If in earlier Soviet Oriental studies a class-based (Marxist-Leninist) viewpoint was adopted as the political-methodological foundation, in Western historiography the tendency toward factual description and moving away from ideologically bounded historical interpretation prevailed. Overall, the achievements of historians, source scholars, archaeologists, ethnologists, and other specialists in our century have laid a sound foundation for understanding the era of Mahmud al-Kashghari.

The third historiographical direction mentioned above pertains to the history of studying Mahmud al-Kashghari's own work as a primary source. The most notable surviving manuscript of Mahmud al-Kashghari's work was published in three volumes using the lithographic (stone printing) method in Istanbul in the years 1915–1917. The Turkish scholar Ali Emiri (1857–1923), who had purchased and prepared the manuscript for scholarly use, entrusted the task of preparing it for publication to his younger contemporary Kilisli Muallim Rifat (1874–1931). From 1915, the year in

which the first volume of the Diwan was published (the year 1333 in the Hijri calendar), its contents began to gradually be studied in the Ottoman Empire and in European scholarly circles. Kilisli Muallim Rifat made a significant contribution to the publication of the work and to promoting its value from the moment the first volume appeared.

The German scholar Martin Hartmann (1851–1918), who had close ties with Istanbul's scholarly circles at the time, wrote his article about Mahmud al-Kashghari's Diwan immediately after the publication of its first volume. This article was translated into Ottoman Turkish and published in September–October 1915 in the then-prestigious scholarly journal *Milli Tettebbu'lar Mecmuasi*. In his article, Martin Hartmann noted that research into the identity of the author had already begun as soon as the first volume of the Diwan appeared, and that he himself had been invited to participate in this endeavor. He wrote about an imam named al-Husayn ibn Khalaf al-Kashghari briefly mentioned in the Diwan. According to this Arabist scholar, the fact that Mahmud al-Kashghari was almost never cited in later Muslim literature can be explained by the tendency of scholars in the Muslim world in later periods to overlook major works written on scholarly topics unrelated to Islam.

Particularly numerous studies on Mahmud al-Kashghari and his legacy were conducted in the Ottoman Empire and in the subsequent Republic of Turkey. Among the first major synthesizing works that made extensive use of Mahmud al-Kashghari's data is a work by the renowned Turkish scholar and thinker Ziya Gokalp (1876–1924). In 1915, he wrote a major article on the social structure of the ancient Turks, drawing extensively on the materials of the Diwan. The book *Islomdan oldingi turk madaniyati* (Pre-Islamic Turkish Culture), the first part of Ziya Gokalp's work *Turk madaniyati tarixi* (History of Turkish Civilization), was published in 1925.

European Oriental studies did not remain indifferent to the publication of the Diwan. The German Arabist Karl Brockelmann (1868–1956) published his article 'Mahmud al-Kashghari's Description of Turkish Verb Formation' in 1919 in a Hungarian Oriental studies journal. His second major article was titled 'Old Turkestani Folk Literature' and pertains to 1919–1920.

Another German professor, G. Bergstrasser (1886–1933), in an article published in 1921 in an Orientalist gazette, noted that the title of Mahmud al-Kashghari's work resembled the title of the work *Diwan al-Adab* by the 10th-century Turkestani linguist Ishaq al-Farabi, and opened the door to the scholarly conclusion that Mahmud al-Kashghari used the methods of his compatriot al-Farabi as a model in compiling his lexicon.

Among scholars in the former USSR, one of the first to turn attention to Mahmud al-Kashghari's legacy was the Orientalist Academician Vasily Vladimirovich Bartold

(1869–1930). In his scholarly lecture of 1921 he made note of Mahmud al-Kashghari and made extensive use of his data in such works as ‘An Outline of the History of the Turkmen People,’ ‘Twelve Lectures on the History of the Turkic Peoples of Central Asia,’ and ‘History of the Turko-Mongol Peoples.’

The prominent Russian-Soviet Turkologist Sergey Yefimovich Malov (1880–1957) also published excerpts from Mahmud al-Kashghari’s Diwan in a small booklet published in Tashkent in 1926. Panteleimon Krestovich Juze (1871–1942) published a valuable article dedicated to Mahmud al-Kashghari’s legacy in Baku in 1926–1927.

In conclusion, Mahmud al-Kashghari’s Diwan Lughat al-Turk has been recognized as one of the most important primary source monuments in world Turkology and Oriental studies. As analyzed in this scholarly article, the lithographic publication of the work in Istanbul in 1915–1917 opened the way for extensive research by scholars from various countries. Turkish, German, Russian, and Uzbekistani scholars turned to Mahmud al-Kashghari’s legacy in their scholarly works and studied even more deeply the history, language, and culture of the Turkic peoples of the 9th–12th centuries.

Research conducted in the field of Kashghari studies demonstrated not only the philological value of the work, but also its incomparable significance from historical-ethnographic and ethno-cultural perspectives. In particular, the data of the Diwan has served as a primary source for illuminating the Kara-Khanid Khanate period and the political and cultural life of that era. Moreover, it has been scientifically proven that Mahmud al-Kashghari in the field of Turkic linguistics continued the traditions of his compatriot Ishaq al-Farabi.

Thus, the comparative and comprehensive research conducted on a global scale on Mahmud al-Kashghari’s legacy has not lost its relevance even today, and new investigations in this field continue to make an important contribution to the development of Turkology and the history of Central Asia.

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